

ISic2963

I.Sicily inscription 2963

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

ash chest

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006.07.25; 2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Fusco, scavo governativo FF.SS. 1882

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 235

Physical Description

A rectangular limestone ash-chest, with lid in the form of a roof with acroteria at each corner, and inscription within a tabula ansata on one long side. Height measurement includes lid.

Dimensions

Height 29 cm

Width 33.5 cm

Depth 28 cm

Layout

Four lines of Latin not perfectly centred within an engraved tabula ansata on the long side of the chest.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Slightly rounded letters with extended strokes; V tends to be rounded at the base, A and N have extended upper strokes, E and F have upward curving horizontal strokes. Interpunct after every word is a four-pointed element

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Q(uintus) · Cornificius ·
2. Q(uinti) · lib(ertus) · Iuvenalis ·
3. vixit · annos · VIII ·
4. pie · salve ·

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Quintus Cornificius Iuvenalis, freedman of Quintus, lived 9 years, a dutiful boy, farewell!

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492322

EDCS 23400460

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.8315 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. Notizie degli scavi di antichità. At 250

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic2963. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4356524>

Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014